

STRATEGIES USED BY SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL ENGLISH TEACHERS FOR COLLABORATIVE WORK

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Strategies used by Senior High School English Teachers for Collaborative Work

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Abstract

This qualitative study aimed to study and identify the strategies of Senior High School English teachers of Holy Trinity College of General Santos City for collaborative work. The researchers purposely selected seven (7) English teachers of the Senior High School Department of Holy Trinity College of General Santos City who are teaching the subjects Practical Research and Reading and Writing. To obtain the results of this study, the researchers utilized a structured and comprehensive interview guide. The participants were then able to share the collaborative works they are implementing, the challenges they face in the implementation of such, and most importantly the strategies for collaborative work. The study established two major themes in the strategies of the participants which are peer evaluation and educational guidance. Considering the findings of the study, it is recommended for the institution to strengthen the integration of the collaborative learning theory in collaborative works inside the classrooms to ensure that the benefits already innate in collaborative work is achieved. Furthermore, the researchers also recommend the future researchers to venture in a comparative study that will analyze and explore the strategies for collaborative work in diverse educational subjects and contexts which can provide a comprehensive understanding into the benefits of intervention or strategies for collaborative work.

Keywords: *collaborative learning theory, collaborative work, peer evaluation, educational guidance.*

Introduction

John Dunne (1624) once stated in a quote that no man is an island, that we are not self-sufficient. We can achieve a lot of things if we collaborate and this is true even in the academe. Collaborative learning through work is defined as learning that involves groups of students and teachers collaborating on joint collective effort (Ahmed, 2021). Working with others is an essential part of the academe that is why collaborative work is often integrated in most classroom set-ups.

A study revealed that collaborative learning can positively impact student engagement and motivation. Students who are engaged in collaborative learning works are more likely to be motivated to learn (Wang & Wu, 2022). Collaborative work allows learners not only to socialize but also develop learning while creating and working on an output assigned to them by their teacher.

There are number of international guidelines that emphasize the importance of collaborative work for students. The Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) in 2015 has stated that group or collaborative work is an essential skill for students to develop in order to succeed in the 21st century workforce. Moreover, as part of the grading system, group or collaborative works are part of the performance tasks which takes 40% of the overall grade of the student (DO 8, S. 2015). Collaborative work is considered integral for the success of 21st century learners which is why it is included in the grading system of the Philippine curriculum in order to ensure that the benefits of collaborative work is achieved in the Philippine educational landscape.

Although some educators recognized that there are certain loopholes in collaborative work such as unfairness in distribution of work, trust, procrastination of members, underwhelming participation, and competition among members which can lead to internal conflict (Slavin, 2018), educators still had high regard in collaborative work as they are strategies that can be employed in order to curb these issues (Harris, 2015). These strategies are employed in order to bring out the best that is already innate in collaborative work.

Research Questions

This research has documented and analyzed the strategies that SHS English teachers of Holy Trinity College of General Santos City employ for collaborative work. This research will answer the following questions:

1. What are the collaborative work being implemented by SHS English teachers in HTC in the following subjects:
 - 1.1 practical research; and
 - 1.2 reading and writing?
2. What are the challenges in implementing collaborative work?
3. What are the strategies in implementing collaborative work?

Literature Review

Collaborative Learning

Collaborative learning is an approach in education in which it utilizes a group of students to work on a particular task while they are learning from each other. This approach actively engages the students to process and work on their tasks with the need for them to

collaborate. Hence, social interaction is essential for collaborative learning to take place (Andreev, 2022). Interaction among the members of a group is important for collaborative learning because without them interacting with each other, it is highly likely that the knowledge and skills of a non-interactive member will not be included in the learning of the group.

Collaborative Work

Collaborative learning is stronger if it will be done through the help of tasks such as collaborative works and if students are given clear instructions in their challenging tasks or collaborative work (Chen et al., 2020). Collaborative learning is learning through interaction and communication however collaborative work must also be utilized in order to ensure that learners do not only communicate but they also proactively interact with each other in creating and completing tasks since the key characteristics of collaborative work is not only allowing communication but most importantly opening interaction and cooperation among its members.

Challenges in Collaborative Work

According to a study by De Vera and Marasigan (2020) conducted among Grade 12 Filipino students, they found out that the challenges mostly faced in collaborative work are trust, competition among members, free-riding students, procrastination of task among each member of the group, underwhelming participation of group members, unfair distribution of work among group members, and internal conflict. These challenges are also reflected in other studies more specifically in a study conducted by Forsell et al. (2021) in which the results of the study showed that teachers have difficulty in evaluating the output of a group because they do not know whose ideas were incorporated or who are the members who really participated in the output. Moreover, students are also faced with the dilemma of not letting a weak performing student participate because of their association of that particular student to his weak performance which might affect the total output of the group.

Strategies in Collaborative Work

As provided in the study of Forsell et al. (2021) and as supported by De Vera & Marasigan (2020) in the Philippine context, the common challenges found in collaborative work are lack of trust, competition, free riding, and procrastination. Although these challenges are common occurrences which are evident in collaborative or group work, these challenges can be mitigated and minimized through various strategies that can be employed by teachers in order to promote effective collaborative work. These strategies include social interaction, accommodation, peer evaluation, and point deduction.

Methodology

This section presents the method used in this phenomenological study. Specifically, the following are included: research design, sampling design, role of the researchers, data collection, face to face interview, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

Participants

The participants of this research were the Senior High School English teachers currently working at Holy Trinity College of General Santos City Senior High School Department. They were chosen using purposive sampling, considering factors such as the subject they are teaching in which should be Practical Research and Reading & Writing. Seven (7) SHS English teachers (originally 8) were selected from the population in order to give their insights and address the research problems that we posed for the academic year 2023- 2024. The Holy Trinity College of General Santos City Senior High School (SHS) English teachers were chosen as they fit the profile covered by the research.

Data Collection

The researchers employed the interview method as a data gathering tool. In terms of data collection method, we conducted the research using an interview guide for asking the participants. We prepared clear questions to help lead the interview toward attaining the research objective. The said interview guide was given to the research adviser for checking the quality and reliability of such a guide. Furthermore, it was only with the approval of the research adviser that we used such guide for our data gathering. The data that we collected from the interviews was analyzed using qualitative methods, including thematic analysis.

Data Analysis

In analyzing the data, the researchers used thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is a qualitative method of data analysis wherein the procedure centers on identification, description, explanation, substantiation, and linkages of themes. It is founded on the view that all information is meaningful and the meaning can be known from associating key ideas (Kampira, 2021). We had then proceeded to conclude and enumerate the strategies of Holy Trinity College of General Santos City Senior High School (SHS) English teachers for collaborative work.

Ethical Considerations

Following the ethical standards set forth in research, we have ensured that the ethical considerations will be followed to prevent engaging in practices that could potentially abuse or exploit the individuals to whom we will conduct research. These principles respect the informed consent, data privacy, voluntary participation, gender sensitivity, and cultural sensitivity of the participants.

Results and Discussion

This section exhibits and elaborately discusses the results, analysis, and interpretations of the gathered data from the seven (7) Senior High School English Teachers of Holy Trinity College of General Santos City for the academic year 2023-2024, who are involved in conducting collaborative works and the strategies they have applied for such. Selected parts of the interview were also provided to support the result. The flow of the presentation and discussion of the gathered data is arranged in parallel to the sequence of the statement of the problem.

Profile of the Senior High School English Teachers

The finding of the study are presented in matrix and tables generated from the thematic analysis.

Matrix 1 shows the profile of the Senior High School English teachers during the in- depth interview. There are five female teachers and two male teachers. Their ages are varied, ranging from 23 years old to 34 years old. In terms of subjects being taught, three participants teach Practical Research only, one participant teach Reading and Writing only, and three participants teach both subjects. Lastly, the work experience of the Senior High School English teachers in this specific institution ranges from seven months to three years. The ideas expressed by the Senior High School English Teachers were used to sort out the insights related to the salient results of the collaborative works they do, the challenges they face by it, and the strategies they use to mitigate such challenges. To uphold confidentiality, code numbers were given to the respective participants.

Table 1. Profile of the Senior High School English Teachers

Code Number	Age	Sex	Subject taught	Length of work experience
SET-01	26	Female	Practical Research	11 months
SET-02	25	Male	Reading and Writing	3 years
SET-03	23	Female	Practical Research	9 months
SET-04	34	Female	Practical Research	8 months
SET-05	23	Female	Practical Research & Reading and Writing	7 months
SET-06	27	Male	Practical Research & Reading and Writing	3 years
SET-07	N/A	Female	Practical Research & Reading and Writing	3 years

Table 1.1. Collaborative Works being implemented by Senior High School English Teachers in HTC for Practical Research

Major Themes	Core Ideas	Frequency
Group Coaching	Think, Pair, and Share	Typical
	Brainstorming	
	Peer Teaching	
Group Reporting	Students prepare a PowerPoint presentation	Variant
	Students conduct in-depth discussion	Variant
Group Project	Students do research writing collaboratively	Variant

Table 2. Challenges in Collaborative Work for Practical Research

Major Theme	Core Ideas	Frequency
Underwhelming Participation	Students lack willingness to participate	Typical
	Some members are unavailable	Typical
Unfair distribution of work	The leaders complain about their workload	Variant
Internal conflict	Members are reclusive	Variant
	Members disagree with each other.	Variant

Table 3. Strategies in Collaborative Work for Practical Research

Major Theme	Core Ideas	Frequency
Peer Evaluation	Leaders evaluate their members	Typical
	Members also evaluate the leader	Typical
Educational Guidance	Teachers assist all groups.	Variant

Table 4. Collaborative Works being Implemented by Senior High School English Teacher in HTC for Reading and Writing

Major Theme	Core Ideas	Frequency
Group Coaching	Students who overperform coach the underperforming students.	Variant

Group Reporting	Students are grouped to allow knowledge sharing	Variant
	Students prepare a PowerPoint presentation	Variant
	Students conduct in-depth discussion.	Variant
Group Project	Students were instructed to create a big book	Variant
	Students were tasked to write their original story.	Variant

Table 5. *Challenges in Collaborative Work for Reading and Writing*

Major Theme	Core Ideas	Frequency
Underwhelming Participation	Students lack willingness to participate	Variant
	Some members are unavailable	Variant
Unfair distribution of work	The leaders complain about their workload	Variant
	Some members do not contribute to the groupwork	Variant
Internal conflict	Members are reclusive	Variant
	Members disagree with each other.	Variant

Table 6. *Strategies in Collaborative Work for Reading and Writing*

Major Theme	Core Ideas	Frequency
Peer Evaluation	Leaders evaluate their members	Variant
	Peer Evaluation is part of the grading system of students	Variant
Educational Guidance	Teachers organize fair grouping.	Variant
	Teachers assist all groups.	Variant

Discussion

This section discusses the insights, implications for collaborative work within the classes of Senior High School English teachers, implications for future researchers, recommendations, and concluding remarks.

In this 21st century world, collaboration is an essential skill for students in order to accomplish many kinds of collaborative work. In order for collaborative work to be done, the students must have the desire and initiative to collaborate with each other. Unfortunately, not everyone has the desire and initiative to collaborate with each other.

This is why the role of the teachers is important for collaborative work to occur. Teachers have different kinds of strategies in order to overcome the challenges that come with collaborative work. Since the teachers in the 21st century are the facilitators of the classroom, and collaborative work is a key component of 21st century education, part of the responsibility of the teachers when it comes to facilitating the classroom is making sure that groups run smoothly without heavily interfering with their affairs. It is because while education is student-centered today, the teachers are still the guardians of education. The teachers today must adjust their mode of safeguarding education, which includes collaborative work.

The reason why it is important to discuss the types, challenges, and benefits for collaborative work in addition to the strategies is because these four elements are related to each other. The types of collaborative work help supplement the strategies of collaborative work, and the challenges faced by Senior High School English teachers for collaborative work help give context as to why these strategies are the ones being used by Senior High School English teachers in facing them. Furthermore, the benefits of the strategies are being discussed because this research wants to know if the strategies used are beneficial for collaborative work.

Therefore, these four elements of collaborative work go hand-in-hand in showing the full picture in the situation of collaborative work of students, and how these strategies used by Senior High School English teachers affect the situation of collaborative work of students.

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